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Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure and Financial Performance of Some Selected Quoted Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the corporate social responsibility disclosure and financial performance of some selected quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria between the periods 2011-2020. The study used secondary data sources which were collected from the annual reports and financial statements of the listed manufacturing companies in the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX Group). The variables used were explained by descriptive analysis, and panel regression analysis was used to determine the impact of environmental disclosure (pollution), social disclosure (staff training costs), and governance disclosure (board size) on the company's financial performance (return on asset, earnings per share). Correlation analysis was used to determine whether there is a relationship between corporate social responsibility disclosure and financial performance. The findings showed a meaningful connection between overall CSR parameters and financial success indicators. The only CSRD metric with a substantial positive correlation to return on assets and earnings per share was social disclosure, while environmental disclosure showed no correlation to financial success. The results led to the conclusion that CSR disclosure measures predicted the financial performance of particular Nigerian manufacturing enterprises. According to the report, encouraged corporate social responsibility disclosure will help companies' brands and reputations. Companies should have fewer board members for better decision-making.

Keywords: *Environmental disclosure, social disclosure, governance disclosure, return on asset, earnings per share.*

1.0 Introduction

Without the support of their various stakeholders, organizations cannot survive in the competitive and globalized climate of today. On the other hand, stakeholders are expected to assess and analyze the financial health of the organization in issue before financial or investment decisions are made. Therefore, in order to expose a company's financial status, it would be necessary to evaluate its financial performance during a specific accounting period. In this context, the phrase "financial performance" refers to a subjective assessment of a company's ability to create income from its assets. A financial indicator is a broad gauge of a company's overall financial health throughout time (Bag & Omrane, 2022).

In recent years, corporate social responsibility (CSR) has gained significant significance. The conventional economic and profit-making objectives of businesses are being supplemented with challenges linked to ethics, sustainability, the environment, and social responsibility. This reveals a significant shift in Kim, Kim, and Qian's (2018) business perspectives. According to Bani-Khaled, El-Dalabee, Al-Olimat, and Al-Shbail (2021), the value of social contributions allows businesses to highlight their strengths and allay community concerns about potential detrimental effects of their operations. The widespread interest in CSR is not seen as a drain on corporate resources, but rather as a means of enhancing the standing and legitimacy of businesses, which will promote success and long-term viability (Mahmood & Orazalin, 2017). According to Abugre&Anlesinya (2019), businesses that enhanced their CSR operations received significant reputational value from their stakeholders, which contributed to overall good economic value.

Disclosure of corporate social responsibility is essentially split into two categories: disclosure that is required and disclosure that is optional. Mandatory disclosure is a legal requirement that is put into operation in developed or western nations. There are legal penalties for not disclosing in some nations. Companies that employ strategies to connect their company operations with the interests of the stakeholders voluntarily disclose their corporate social responsibility (CSR) activities. Although pursuing CSR disclosure is a decision made voluntarily by the company, social pressure has led many businesses in the modern era to incorporate CSR disclosures into their strategy goals (Grayson & Hodges, 2017).

Making money and enhancing financial performance are the objectives of each and every business. There are many ways a firm can achieve this. One of the activities, corporate social responsibility (CSR) disclosure, was divided into sub-variables for the purpose of this study, including environmental, social, and governance disclosures. Businesses may cause environmental issues as a result of their activities, which may have an effect on the neighborhood in which they operate as well as the company's reputation or image over time. For instance, if a business operated in a neighborhood or community and its operations damaged the air, the water, or the means of subsistence of the community, the host community can definitely be dissatisfied with the business and will eventually be less likely to frequent it.

According to Almarah, Norwani, Khalid, and Aljajawy (2019), one of the major factors contributing to the demise of numerous industrial companies is the lack of transparency and disclosure in their financial reports and statements. This is in addition to the fact that they failed to present actual data and information that accurately reflected their financial situation. If the corporation engages in these activities without identifying ways to lessen the destructions, there will be no CSR disclosure in the financial statement. In that case, the company's financial performance will suffer as a result of failing to disclose its CSR in its accounts or financial statements. Investors who want to invest in this company but are aware that its activities have had a negative net impact on the community (the host community) and that their financial statements do not disclose the modification of such activities will refrain from doing so because the company carried out its operations at the expense of the community with no improvement or reform.

Employees who were not given training by the company on the risks that were affecting their surroundings and host communities would not be aware of the disaster(s) they had caused to society, which led to low patronage, poor inhabitation, and other problems that decreased their financial performance and, as a result, the performance of company activities. Some companies refused to train their personnel, which had an effect on both the productivity of the employees and the revenue of the company. The organization may become more profitable if employees have the necessary training, initiative, and skills to carry out production.

According to Jensen (2016) and Yermack (2016), as boards of directors grow, they struggle more to implement CSR initiatives since they have less power over management. Over time, poor management will have a negative impact on financial performance. A smaller board of directors is also more likely than a bigger one to be in charge of overseeing a corporation's operations (CSR), according to Vaefas (2017). It may take longer for larger

boards of directors to respond to choices that call for an immediate course of action, making it more difficult to demonstrate governance in their financial statements.

CSR and financial success may be positively, negatively, inconsistently, or neutrally correlated. As a result, we can divide research into three categories: studies that found a solid connection (Strouhal, Gurvit, Nikitina-Kalamäe, & Startseva, 2015; Khlif, Guidara, & Souissi, 2015; and King'wara, 2020) suggested that promoting a company's CSR improves its value and reputation, which in turn enhances its long-term financial performance. Those who received outcomes that were inconsistent (Sekhon & Kathuria, 2019). A neutral conclusion (Kolsi & Attayah, 2018) states that there is no connection between CSR and financial performance.

The primary goal of this study was to identify the patterns of relationships between manufacturing enterprises in Nigeria that were chosen for the study and their financial performance. Second, look into how corporate social responsibility disclosure has affected the overall financial performance of a few Nigerian manufacturing companies as well as the financial performance of individual enterprises.

2.1 Literature Review

(Net Income + Interest Expense) / Average Total Assets (Ebe, Celestine, Ada, Uzodinma and Ifeoma, 2021) is the formula used to determine return on asset. In the study, it was discovered that there was a bad correlation between return on assets (ROA) and corporate social responsibility disclosure (CSR) (Ebe, Celestine, Ada, Uzodinma & Ifeoma, 2021). According to Onyali, Okerekeoti, and Uchegbu's 2020 study assessment of the factors that effectively influence social responsibility disclosure of listed consumer goods firms on the Nigerian stock exchange, there is a positive and significant correlation between ROA and CSR. According to the study, there is a positive and significant relationship between ROA and CSR (Onyali, Okerekeoti, & Uchegbu, 2020). Return on Assets (ROA) is one of the profitability ratios in the financial statements, according to Shrivastava, Kumar, and Kumar (2017). This ratio is frequently discussed since it shows how successful a firm is at turning a profit.

Earnings statistics continue to be the most important metric for determining a company's value (Narullia, Subekti, Azizah, & Purnamasari, 2019). According to Handoyo (2020), CSR performance was found to be positively correlated with EPS. Fauzan and Kuswanto (2018) reached the same conclusion after doing earlier research in Indonesia. In Nigeria, CSR has a negligible but beneficial effect on manufacturing companies' earnings per share (Emamoke & Omodero, 2021). Bag and Omrane (2022) found that the study supported earlier research findings (Siueia, Wang & Deladem, 2019; Maqbool & Zameer, 2018) by showing a positive correlation between CSR and EPS. CSR should therefore be considered a corporate policy rather than a choice.

Corporate environmental policies or concerns, pollution management in corporate operations, resource conservation, mitigation of the environmental effects of manufacturing processes or natural resources, emissions data, waste water discharge, and waste treatment (Ta & Bui, 2018). The world's most pressing issue, environmental pollution is not new and is mostly caused by both natural and human forces. There is a very good chance that the development of the industry will have positive or negative effects on the environment, society, investors, and potential investors. By illegally dumping waste from their enterprises into waterways, many businesses continue to harm the environment. Numerous studies on numerous environmental concerns have forced businesses to increase their attention to environmental and ecological preservation (Kraus, Rehman & Garca, 2020). ROA is negatively impacted by the environmental component of CSR (Moosa, He, & Arrive, 2021). It was shown that there was little correlation between ROA, EPS, and environmental disclosure (Sameer, 2021).

Information on policies for seasonal or contractual employees or plans to hire seasonal or contractual employees, working conditions, workers' health care, training, financial assistance for housing, daily allowance for employees, maternity leaves, holidays, and recruitment/job opportunities for women, ethnic minorities, or special interest groups (Ta & Bui, 2018). According to Moosa, He, and Arrive (2002), the CSR dimension of employees has a favorable but negligible connection with ROA. Compared to other activities like

environmental, educational, and volunteer work, employee incentives have a positive impact on ROA (Cherian et al. 2019).

The growth in corporate governance disclosure might be viewed as a strategy by firms to win back shareholders' trust. Effective management oversight by the board of directors should follow good corporate governance, and the board of directors and management should get the right incentives to work toward corporate and shareholder-friendly goals. 2015 (Andersson & Daouda). The governance component of CSR exhibited a poor and negligible correlation with ROA (Moosa, He, & Arrive, 2021). According to Cherian et al. 2019 there is a strong positive association between ROA and GD.

It has long been recognized that a company's size plays a significant role in its CSR disclosure. This is because the extent of a company's corporate operations and, consequently, the scope of its CSR reporting, are influenced by its size. Large organizations under higher pressure to report CSR than small businesses do since they are of particular interest to a wider range of social groups and must do so in order to justify their operations (Onyali et al., 2020). According to Badulescu, Badulescu, Saveanu, and Hatos (2018), there is a positive correlation between firm size and CSR disclosure. To put it another way, a company is less likely to practice corporate social responsibility the younger it is. According to research by Sekhon and Kathuria (2019), a positive association between a company's size and CSR has been found. The variance in CSR performance is barely impacted by the company's size (Handoyo, 2020).

Financial leverage is a factor that affects a firm's financial success, according to the study. In order to analyze the relationship between CSR disclosure and financial success, financial leverage is required. Leverage is the term for a number of financial tools or borrowed funds used to raise a company's prospective investment return (Onyali et al., 2020). Corporate social responsibility suffered as a result of leverage (Sekhon & Kathuria, 2019). Bag and Omrane (2022) found that the study supported earlier research findings (e.g. Siueia et al. 2019, Maqbool&Zameer, 2018) by showing a positive link between CSR and financial leverage. Disclosure of corporate social responsibility and leverage have a significant and favorable relationship (Onyali et al., 2020). ROA is significantly and negatively impacted by leverage (King'wara, 2020).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

In order to examine the financial performance of publicly traded industrial enterprises, this study used stakeholder theory. Despite the fact that the stakeholder idea has been the subject of in-depth study for the past 20 years, it is typically characterized as the antithesis of the shareholder (or stockholder) model. In order to perform well, managers must pay attention to a variety of stakeholders, and these managers have obligations to stakeholders that include but go beyond shareholders (Jones, 2002). These two basic principles are summarized by other stakeholder theorists as follows. Stakeholder theory is largely focused on three premises from a business perspective: organizations have stakeholder groups that influence and are influenced by them; interactions between stakeholder groups have an effect on both the organization and particular stakeholders; and perspectives of important stakeholders have an impact on the viability of strategic options (Haberberg and Rieple, 2001; Simmons, 2004). The stakeholder approach, on the other hand, expands the shareholder model rather than rejecting profitability as a business goal. The stakeholder approach acknowledges that shareholders have a legitimate claim, but it rejects the notion that they should have exclusive or preferential rights over those of other legitimate claimants (Hummels, 1998).

2.3 Conceptual Framework

INDEPENDENT VARIABLES DEPENDENT VARIABLES

Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure (CSR D)

Financial Performance

Source: Author’s Conceptualization, 2023

3.0 Methodology

Population and sample

The population of this study, which was released on (Statista, 2022) consisted of one hundred seventy-seven (177) companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. The population was decreased in order to establish a sample size for the study since it is thought to be excessively large. In order to expose important information that cannot be learned from other possibilities, specific scenarios, people, or events were carefully picked for the study's judgmental sampling (Maxwell, 1996). The sample contains cases that were thought to be deserving of inclusion. Nigerian Breweries, Lafarge Plc, Nestle Nigeria, Dangote Cement, Unilever, and these companies were picked. Additionally, these companies were chosen since they have been around for a while and have access to enough data. The results of the survey conducted among the aforementioned companies were representative of the entire study population.

Model Specification

Owolabi (2010) discovered the following CSR disclosures in financial statements, which were coded and defined below, in a thorough review of corporate social responsibility disclosure data for selected public firms in Nigeria sampled from 2011 to 2020. The functional form of the model was modified to analyze the effects of certain CSR activity variants that are frequently reported in financial statements on particular business performance indicators, and it is as follows:

$$FP = f(CSRD)$$

Model I

$$\begin{aligned} \text{LogROA}_{it} &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{LogENVD}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{LogSOD}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{LogGOVD}_{it} + \beta_4 \text{LogLEV}_{it} + \beta_5 \text{LogFS}_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \\ \text{LogEPS}_{it} &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{LogENVD}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{LogSOD}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{LogGOVD}_{it} + \beta_4 \text{LogLEV}_{it} + \beta_5 \text{LogFS}_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \end{aligned}$$

Where:

ROA = Return on asset

EPS = Earnings per shares

ENVD – Environmental Disclosure

SOD = Social Disclosure

GOVD = Governance Disclosure

LEV = Leverage

FS = Firm Size

Model II

To determine the company specific impact of corporate social responsibility disclosure on Return on Asset Multiple regression analysis was used. The equation for each company is given as follows

$$\text{LogROA}_{LAFt} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{LogENVD}_{LAFt} + \beta_2 \text{LogSOD}_{LAFt} + \beta_3 \text{LogGOVD}_{LAFt} + \beta_4 \text{LogLEV}_{LAFt} + \beta_5 \text{LogFS}_{LAFt} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad 3.8$$

$$\text{LogROA}_{DANTt} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{LogENVD}_{DANTt} + \beta_2 \text{LogSOD}_{DANTt} + \beta_3 \text{LogGOVD}_{DANTt} + \beta_4 \text{LogLEV}_{DANTt} + \beta_5 \text{LogFS}_{DANTt} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad 3.9$$

$$\text{LogROA}_{NBt} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{LogENVD}_{NBt} + \beta_2 \text{LogSOD}_{NBt} + \beta_3 \text{LogGOVD}_{NBt} + \beta_4 \text{LogLEV}_{MBt} + \beta_5 \text{LogFS}_{NBt} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad 3.10$$

$$\text{LogROA}_{UNLt} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{LogENVD}_{UNLt} + \beta_2 \text{LogSOD}_{UNLt} + \beta_3 \text{LogGOVD}_{UNLt} + \beta_4 \text{LogLEV}_{UNLt} + \beta_5 \text{LogFS}_{UNLt} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad 3.11$$

$$\text{LogROA}_{NEStt} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{LogENVD}_{LNEStt} + \beta_2 \text{LogSOD}_{LNEStt} + \beta_3 \text{LogGOVD}_{LNEStt} + \beta_4 \text{LogLEV}_{NEStt} + \beta_5 \text{LogFS}_{NEStt} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad 3.12$$

Where LAF denotes Lafarge, DAN represent Dangote, NB represent Nigerian Breweries, UNL stands for Unilever and NES represents Nestle while all other variables remain are denoted.

Model III

To determine the company specific impact of corporate social responsibility disclosure on Earnings per share multiple regression analysis was used. The equation for each company is given as follows

$$\text{LogEPS}_{LAFt} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{LogENVD}_{LAFt} + \beta_2 \text{LogSOD}_{LAFt} + \beta_3 \text{LogGOVD}_{LAFt} + \beta_4 \text{LogLEV}_{LAFt} + \beta_5 \text{LogFS}_{LAFt} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad 3.13$$

$$\text{LogEPS}_{DANTt} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{LogENVD}_{DANTt} + \beta_2 \text{LogSOD}_{DANTt} + \beta_3 \text{LogGOVD}_{DANTt} + \beta_4 \text{LogLEV}_{DANTt} + \beta_5 \text{LogFS}_{DANTt} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad 3.14$$

$$\text{LogEPS}_{NBt} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{LogENVD}_{NBt} + \beta_2 \text{LogSOD}_{NBt} + \beta_3 \text{LogGOVD}_{NBt} + \beta_4 \text{LogLEV}_{MBt} + \beta_5 \text{LogFS}_{NBt} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad 3.15$$

$$\text{LogEPS}_{UNLt} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{LogENVD}_{UNLt} + \beta_2 \text{LogSOD}_{UNLt} + \beta_3 \text{LogGOVD}_{UNLt} + \beta_4 \text{LogLEV}_{UNLt} + \beta_5 \text{LogFS}_{UNLt} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad 3.16$$

$$\text{LogEPS}_{NEStt} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{LogENVD}_{LNEStt} + \beta_2 \text{LogSOD}_{LNEStt} + \beta_3 \text{LogGOVD}_{LNEStt} + \beta_4 \text{LogLEV}_{NEStt} + \beta_5 \text{LogFS}_{NEStt} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad 3.17$$

4.0 Results and Discussions

4.1 Descriptive Statistics of Variables

Table 4.1 showed the descriptive statistics for the variables and as observed, the highest mean for the return on asset was reported in Dangote with 0.206 followed by Nestle with 0.200 then Nigerian Breweries by 0.099. Unilever recorded the least value on the return on asset with 0.057. The maximum value on the return on asset was recorded in Dangote with 0.279 followed by Nestle with 0.264 then Nigerian Breweries with 0.178. The minimum value of the return on asset was reported in in Unilever with – 0.071.

In relation to earning per shares of the selected companies, the highest mean value was recorded in Nestle with 34.747 followed by Dangote with 15.228. The highest maximum value was reported in Nestle also with 57.630 while the minimum value was reported in Lafarge with -2.400. In terms of environmental disclosure of the companies, the maximum value was reported in Dangote while the minimum value was recorded in Lafarge. The mean for social disclosure was higher in Nigerian Breweries. The maximum value was recorded in Dangote with 3174050 followed by Nigerian Breweries 2233463. The minimum value is recorded in Lafarge, Dangote and Unilever with no value disclosed. As regard governance disclosure, the company with the highest mean value was Nigerian Breweries with 13.60. The maximum value was reported in Lafarge with 18.000 followed by Dangote and Nigerian Breweries with 16.000 respectively. The minimum value was recorded in Dangote and Nestle with 7.000 respectively.

Table 4.1. Descriptive analysis of variables

Company	Mean	Std. Dev	Min	Max
Return on Asset				
Lafarge	0.059	0.055	-0.021	0.175
Dangote	0.206	0.053	0.119	0.279
Nigerian Breweries	0.099	0.055	0.016	0.178
Unilever	0.057	0.076	-0.071	0.170
Nestle	0.200	0.060	0.047	0.264
Panel	0.125	0.008	-0.071	0.279
Earnings Per Shares				
Lafarge	3.889	3.841	-2.400	9.340
Dangote	15.228	6.537	7.130	28.250
Nigerian Breweries	3.934	1.644	0.940	5.700
Unilever	0.761	1.052	-1.290	1.840
Nestle	34.747	15.514	10.000	57.630
Panel	11.711	14.683	-2.400	57.630
Environmental Disclosure				
Lafarge	511001.1	409389.6	0.0000	1260962.
Dangote	101373.1	664326.9	260539.0	2507510.
Nigerian Breweries	1640068.7	173467.0	40400.00	634547.0
Unilever	83072.70	80405.62	18676.00	243709.0
Nestle	106383.0	243439.0	2088.000	797710.0
Panel	375651.1	507618.2	0.00000	2507510.
Social Disclosure				
Lafarge	150190.4	177164.2	0.00000	405987.0
Dangote	598317.3	976732.9	0.00000	3174050.
Nigerian Breweries	1777803.	404926.6	1032301.	2233463.

Unilever	157870.5	170673.1	0.00000	443552.0
Nestle	1150544.	329005.8	665503.0	1788658.
Panel	766945.0	796271.4	0.00000	3174050.
Governance Disclosure				
Lafarge	13.50	2.798	11.000	18.000
Dangote	12.00	3.055	7.000	16.000
Nigerian Breweries	13.60	1.955	11.000	16.000
Unilever	9.900	1.370	8.000	12.000
Nestle	8.400	0.699	7.000	9.000
Panel	11.48	2.922	7.000	18.000

Source: Author's computation, 2023

4.2 Correlation Analysis

The result presented in table 4.2 showed that there is a significant relationship between corporate social responsibility disclosure and financial performance.

Table 4.2: Correlation Result between corporate social responsibility disclosure and financial performance

Variables	ROA	EPS	LEV	FS	ENVD	SOD	GOVD
ROA	1.000						
EPS	0.809*** (0.000)	1.000					
LEV	0.017 (0.908)	0.058 (0.637)	1.000				
FS	0.147 (0.307)	0.204 (0.156)	-0.654*** (0.000)	1.000			
ENVD	0.142 (0.328)	0.049 (0.735)	-0.445** (0.001)	0.409*** (0.003)	1.000		
SOD	0.044* (0.072)	0.248* (0.085)	-0.039 (0.788)	0.183 (0.259)	0.085 (0.557)	1.000	
GOVD	-0.229** (0.010)	-0.188** (0.019)	-0.507*** (0.000)	0.456*** (0.001)	0.305** (0.031)	0.049 (0.735)	1.000

Source: Author's computation, 2023

4.3 Regression Results

Impact of Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure on Return on Asset (Aggregate)

Table 4.3 presented the outcome of the impact of corporate social responsibility disclosure on return on asset of the selected firm in terms of their aggregate impact. From the result, environmental disclosure impacted positively on the return on asset. Social disclosure from the result showed a positive impact on return on asset. Governance disclosure another measure used for corporate social responsibility disclosure showed a positive impact on return on asset in the selected manufacturing companies. In terms of the control variables used in the study, leverage impacted negatively on the return on asset, and firm size displayed a positive but insignificant relationship with the return on asset of the selected firms.

The coefficient of correlation which is the R-squared showed that about 45% in the variation of return on asset of the company is explained by environmental disclosure, social disclosure, governance disclosure, leverage and the firm size of the selected listed companies.

Table 4.3: Panel Least Square Result on ROA

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob
ENV	0.016	0.014337	1.079	0.286
SOD	0.003	0.00509	0.056	0.056
GOV	0.316	0.125506	2.515	0.015
LEV	-0.016	0.060404	-0.272	0.786
FS	0.044	0.018607	0.272	0.787
R²	0.454			

Source: Author’s computation, 2023

Impact of Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure on Earning Per Shares (Aggregate)

Table 4.4 displayed the outcome of the impact of corporate social responsibility disclosure on earning per shares of the selected firm in terms of their aggregate impact. From the result, environmental, governance and firm size had a positive and significant impact on earnings per share. This showed that these variables were important factors to earnings per share. Social disclosure showed a positive and insignificant impact on earnings per share. This means that it was not an important factor that determined the behavior of earnings per share. Leverage negatively and insignificantly impacted on earnings per share.

The R-squared value showed that about 51% in the variation of earnings per shares is accounted for by environmental disclosure, social disclosure, governance disclosure, leverage rave and firm size.

Table 4.4: Regression result on the impact of social responsibility disclosure on EPS

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob
ENV	0.018	0.058056	0.305	0.062
SOD	0.029	0.020654	1.423	0.162
GOV	0.972	0.526707	1.845	0.072
LEV	-0.455	0.369525	-1.232	0.225
FS	0.345	0.144936	2.381	0.022
R²	0.511			

Source: Author’s computation, 2023

4.4 Company Specific Results

Impact of corporate social responsibility disclosure on return on asset (company’s specific impact)

Table 4.5 showed the companies specific results on the impact of corporate social responsibility disclosure on return on asset.As reported, environmental disclosure impacted positively on return on asset for all the selected listed companies. .However, the result was only significant for Lafarge and Unilever with $\rho < 0.1$ and with $\rho < 0.05$ respectively. Based on the magnitude, the impact was more felt in Unilever followed by Dangote and Nestle. The least impact was felt in Lafarge with 0.003%.With respect to social disclosure, the result was significant for Dangote, Nigerian Breweries, and Nestle with $\rho < 0.1$, $\rho < 0.1$ and $\rho < 0.1$ respectively. Looking on the magnitude of the impact, the result showed that the impact was more severe in Nestle. The least company with the lowest magnitude of impact was Dangote with 0.005%.Governance disclosure also displayed a positive impact on all the selected listed companies with return on asset.The result was significant for Lafarge and Nestle.The magnitude of the impact was more felt in Nestle,followed by Unilever, then Nigerian Breweries with 0.154%.Leverage impacted positively on the return on asset for all the selected listed companies.The result was however significant for only Lafarge and Nestle with $\rho < 0.05$ respectively.Firm size was also positively

related with the return on asset for all the selected listed companies. However, the result was significant for Lafarge, Nigerian Breweries and Nestle.

Table 4.5: Regression Result on Company specific impact on return on asset

	Lafarge	Dangote	Nigerian Breweries	Unilever	Nestle
ENV	0.003 (0.068)	0.035 (0.622)	0.012 (0.488)	0.077 (0.041)	0.034 (0.387)
SOD	0.007 (0.270)	0.005 (0.052)	0.023 (0.078)	0.021 (0.536)	0.156 (0.076)
GOV	0.127 (0.039)	0.116 (0.855)	0.154 (0.286)	0.565 (0.266)	0.787 (0.043)
LEV	0.283 (0.033)	0.714 (0.183)	0.167 (0.406)	0.028 (0.923)	0.753 (0.016)
FS	0.187 (0.017)	0.233 (0.529)	0.529 (0.001)	0.088 (0.875)	0.142 (0.079)
R²	0.899	0.592	0.976	0.712	0.601

Source: Author’s computation 2023

Impact of corporate social responsibility disclosure on Earnings Per Shares (company’s specific impact)

Table 4.6 showed the companies specific results on the impact of corporate social responsibility disclosure on earnings per shares. As reported, environmental disclosure impacted positively on the earnings per share for all the selected listed companies. Based on the magnitude, the effect was more felt in Unilever followed by Nestle. The least impact was felt in Dangote. In the area of social disclosure, the result was positively related with the earning per shares for all the listed manufacturing companies selected for the study. The least company with the lowest magnitude of impact was Dangote with 0.005%. Governance disclosure also displayed a positive impact on all the selected listed companies with earnings per shares. The magnitude of the impact was more felt in Nestle, followed by Unilever, then Lafarge. Leverage impacted negatively on the earnings per shares for all the selected listed companies. The result was however, significant for Lafarge, and Nigerian Breweries at 1% and 5% respectively. Firm size was also positively related with earnings per shares for all the selected listed companies. However, the result showed that all other companies had a significant impact except for Dangote Cement.

Table 4.6: Regression Result (Company's Specific)

	LAFARGE	DANGOTE	NIGERIAN BREWERIES	UNILEVER	NESTLE
ENV	0.033 (0.014)	0.005 (0.069)	0.009 (0.025)	0.067 (0.038)	0.119 (0.062)
SOD	0.039 (0.004)	0.005 (0.035)	0.162 (0.415)	0.053 (0.074)	0.229 (0.091)
GOV	0.658 (0.014)	0.192 (0.067)	0.523 (0.049)	1.136 (0.207)	1.527 (0.621)
LEV	-1.543 (0.001)	-0.785 (0.383)	-0.484 (0.018)	-0.316 (0.533)	-2.079 (0.223)
FS	0.705 (0.003)	0.441 (0.512)	0.668 (0.013)	0.569 (0.066)	1.178 (0.026)
R²	0.784	0.813	0.759	0.586	0.580

Source: Author’s computation 2023

4.5 Comparative Analysis

The comparative analysis of the company’s ranks was presented in Table 4.7 and Table 4.8 respectively. Lafarge ranked fifth in respect to environmental disclosure effect on return on asset, fourth with respect to social

disclosure as well as governance disclosure respectively. Dangote cement ranked second with respect to environmental disclosure, fifth in terms of both social disclosure and governance disclosure respectively. Nigerian Breweries ranked fourth with respect to environmental disclosure, second in social disclosure and third in respect to governance disclosure respectively. As regarded Unilever, the company ranked first in terms of environmental disclosure, third in social disclosure and second in governance disclosure respectively. Nestle Nigeria ranked third in environmental disclosure, first in all the social responsibility disclosure and governance disclosure.

Table 4.7: Comparative Analysis (Return on Asset)

ENVIRONMENTAL DISCLOSURE			SOCIAL DISCLOSURE			GOVERNANCE DISCLOSURE		
Company	Coeff	Rank	Company	Coeff	Rank	Company	Coeff	Rank
Unilever	0.077	1 st	Nestle	0.156	1 st	Nestle	0.787	1 st
Dangote	0.035	2 nd	Nigerian Breweries	0.023	2 nd	Unilever	0.565	2 nd
Nestle	0.034	3 rd	Unilever	0.021	3 rd	Nigerian Breweries	0.154	3 rd
Nigerian Breweries	0.012	4 th	Lafarge	0.007	4 th	Lafarge	0.127	4 th
Lafarge	0.003	5 th	Dangote	0.005	5 th	Dangote	0.116	5 th

Source: Author’s computation 2023

For earnings per shares, Lafarge ranked third in respect to environmental disclosure, fourth with respect to social disclosure and third in governance disclosure respectively. Dangote cement ranked fifth with respect to environmental disclosure, social disclosure as well as governance disclosure. Nigerian Breweries ranked fourth with respect to environmental disclosure, second in social disclosure and fourth in respect to governance disclosure respectively. As regards Unilever, the company ranked second in terms of environmental disclosure, third in social disclosure and second in governance disclosure respectively. Nestle Nigeria ranked first in all the social responsibility disclosure measures.

Table 4.8: Comparative Analysis (Earnings per share)

ENVIRONMENTAL DISCLOSURE			SOCIAL DISCLOSURE			GOVERNANCE DISCLOSURE		
Company	Coeff	Rank	Company	Coeff	Rank	Company	Coeff	Rank
Nestle	0.119	1 st	Nestle	0.229	1 st	Nestle	1.527	1 st
Unilever	0.067	2 nd	Nigerian Breweries	0.162	2 nd	Unilever	1.136	2 nd
Lafarge	0.033	3 rd	Unilever	0.053	3 rd	Lafarge	0.658	3 rd
Nigerian Breweries	0.009	4 th	Lafarge	0.039	4 th	Nigerian Breweries	0.523	4 th
Dangote	0.005	5 th	Dangote	0.005	5 th	Dangote	0.192	5 th

Source: Author’s computation 2023

4.6 Test of Hypotheses

Hypotheses one

The result was presented in Table 4.9 where the result showed that the corporate social responsibility disclosure variables were significantly related at 5% with return on asset and earnings per share for both governance disclosure and social disclosure but insignificant with environmental disclosure. This showed that the null hypothesis be rejected and hence, the study concluded that corporate social responsibility disclosure had significant relationship with the return on asset and earnings per share of the selected listed companies. The findings agreed with (Siueia et al., 2018; Onyali et al., 2020).

Table 4.9: Correlation between corporate social responsibility disclosure and ROA

Variables	N	r	ρ	Decision
ROA	50			
ENVD	50	0.142	0.328	Accept H_0
SOD	50	0.044	0.072	Reject H_0
GOVD	50	-0.229	0.010	Reject H_0
EPS	50			
ENVD	50	0.049	0.735	Accept H_0
SOD	50	0.248	0.085	Reject H_0
GOVD	50	-0.188	0.019	Reject H_0

Source: Author's computation, 2023

Hypotheses two

As presented in Table 4.10, it showed that corporate social responsibility disclosure had a significant impact on the Return on Asset of the selected listed manufacturing companies. Based on this result, the null hypothesis of no significant impact of corporate social responsibility disclosure on Return on Asset was rejected. The findings supported the outcomes by (Khan, et al, 2022). It also showed that corporate social responsibility disclosure had a significant impact on the Earnings per shares of the selected listed manufacturing companies. Based on this result, the null hypothesis of no significant impact of corporate social responsibility disclosure on Earnings per share was rejected. The findings agreed with (Kludacz-Alessandri, & Cygańska, 2021).

Table 4.10 Impact of CSRD on ROA and EPS

Variables	N	F-Statistics	ρ	Decision
Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure	50	8.354	0.032	Reject H_0
Return on Asset	50			
Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure	50	12.451	0.032	Reject H_0
Earnings per share	50			

Source: Author's computation, 2023

5.0 Conclusion

This implied that the practice of effective corporate social responsibility disclosure (CSRD) by listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria can enhance a more peaceful coexistence and efficient operations of the companies in their host communities. Corporate social responsibility disclosure had significant relationship with financial performance of the selected manufacturing companies.

Corporate social responsibility disclosure had a considerable effect on the selected manufacturing businesses' earnings per share. A smooth operation of the businesses in their host communities can be improved by the listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria's practice of effective corporate social responsibility disclosure (CSRD).

5.1 Recommendations

- i. It is advised to raise the amount spent on environmental initiatives and appropriately disclose them in the yearly reports in light of the serious risks posed by environmental deterioration globally and in Nigeria in particular.
- ii. Companies should have fewer board members in order to make quick decisions more successfully.
- iii. The study recommended, among other things, that corporate social responsibility disclosure should be encouraged in order to improve the brand and image reputation of the companies. This is because their CSR disclosure had a positive and significant impact on the financial performance of the chosen listed firms in Nigeria.

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